

Journal of Social and Political Sciences

Zibo, B. S., Nweke, O. C., & Appiah, E. K. A. (2024). Political Vigilantism in Ghana: A Threat to National Security and Democratic Processes. *Journal of Social and Political Sciences*, 7(3), 165-173.

ISSN 2615-3718

DOI: 10.31014/aior.1991.07.03.513

The online version of this article can be found at:

<https://www.asianinstituteofresearch.org/>

Published by:
The Asian Institute of Research

The *Journal of Social and Political Sciences* is an Open Access publication. It may be read, copied, and distributed free of charge according to the conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

The Asian Institute of Research *Social and Political Sciences* is a peer-reviewed International Journal. The journal covers scholarly articles in the fields of Social and Political Sciences, which include, but are not limited to, Anthropology, Government Studies, Political Sciences, Sociology, International Relations, Public Administration, History, Philosophy, Arts, Education, Linguistics, and Cultural Studies. As the journal is Open Access, it ensures high visibility and the increase of citations for all research articles published. The *Journal of Social and Political Sciences* aims to facilitate scholarly work on recent theoretical and practical aspects of Social and Political Sciences.

ASIAN INSTITUTE OF RESEARCH
Connecting Scholars Worldwide

Political Vigilantism in Ghana: A Threat to National Security and Democratic Processes

Bashiru Salifu Zibo¹, Ogochukwu C. Nweke², Emmanuel Kweku Amoako Appiah³

¹ Chief Inspector, Ghana Police Service, Accra Regional Command; Lecturer, Faculty of Law, Governance and International Relations, Kings University College (KUC), Accra, Ghana; Centre for Distant and e-Learning, University of Education Winneba, Kasoa, Ghana

² Lecturer, School of Business, Leadership and Legal Studies (SBLL), Regent University College of Science and Technology, Accra, Ghana; Faculty of Law, Governance and International Relations, Kings University College (KUC), Accra, Ghana; <https://orcid.org/0009-0009-6956-5345>

³ Revenue Officer (RO), Customs Division, Ghana Revenue Authority; Revenue Officer (RO), LLM commercial and corporate law (UG), MSc Oil and Gas Resource Management (UCC)LLB and BA (History and Linguistics)-UG. PhD Student, UNICAF University, Malawi

Abstract

The presence of political vigilantism remains a critical challenge to Ghana's national security, particularly during the electoral period. This paper has investigated political vigilantism focusing on the characteristics and behaviour of structured factions such as the Delta Force and Azorka Boys who purport to be party affiliates. The study utilised a mixed research methodology, involving interviews, surveys, and document analysis, to identify the major determinants that foster the growth of vigilante groups in Ghana. From the study, political violence arises from intense political competition, socio-economic disparities, cultural factors, and weak state structures. Though political vigilantism has violent and non-violent outcomes, all the scenarios have the same implications of undermining public safety, state authority, and public trust in the security agencies. The paper validated these findings using the Delta Force's attack on a Kumasi court and the 2020 general election chaotic events to show the extent of the problem. It concludes by promoting policy recommendations that strengthen the legal frameworks, enhance the capacity of the law enforcement agencies, ensure political accountability, increase investment in community engagement, and deepen international cooperation. As Ghana approaches the 2024 general elections, the efficacy of these safeguards will be vital in guaranteeing a peaceful, free and fair democratic process.

Keywords: Democratic Processes, Election Violence, Ghana; Law Enforcement, National Security, Political Vigilantism

1. Introduction

In Ghana, political vigilantism has grown to be a source of grave concern, especially during elections. Political parties frequently create or co-opt vigilante organisations, which are usually organised to maintain security,

mobilise followers, and even threaten adversaries. These groups operate beyond the formal state apparatus and resort to violence, often stemming democratic processes in a profound way as well as social stability.

Apart from these few instances, the issue of political vigilantism in Ghana dates back to our early years of independence where violent clashes did occur as a result. The confrontations evolved into organized groups with easily identifiable leaders and methods over the years. Vigilante groups entered the Ghanaian political lexicon morphed at some point in time with the advent of multi-party democracy after three decades of military occupation. The high stakes of political competition also gave rise to groups like the Azorka Boys, Delta Force and Invisible Forces famous for their activities. Such groups not only pose a threat to the peace during elections but also challenge the legitimacy of state security institutions.

Azorka Boys for example are aligned with the National Democratic Congress (NDC) and Delta Force, Invisible Forces in different contexts support the New Patriotic Party (NPP). These organizations have been connected to incidents of violence, such as attacks on political adversaries, planned property destruction and the crashing of political events. The activities of these groups underscore how far political parties are willing to advance their interests to the detriment of national security and democratic consolidation (Aning & Larney, 2021).

1.1. Importance of the Study

Understanding the growing issue of political vigilantism in Ghana is critical for a few reasons. Firstly, it makes progress on a fundamental security problem that erodes the rule of law and democratic control. The dynamics and operations of these groups can be analysed in order to make policies that act against their influence. Secondly, the article has relevance for broader debates on political violence and security in sub-Saharan Africa which are relevant to comparable situations elsewhere. Finally, it forms a foundation for priming an approach to enhance the national security and political stability.

Political vigilantism disrupts the peace obviously but even worse, it undermines public confidence in our political institutions and that fact as to whether or not this (state) can keep us all safe. This is a situation of mutual distrust which could create a vicious cycle as citizens rely more and more on non-state actors for security with an inevitable weakening in the authority of the state. The study, is in a nutshell, trying to understand the drivers and effects of political vigilantism towards efforts aimed at (re)building public trust over time in state institutions.

1.2. Objectives of Study

The primary aim of this study is to analyse the implications of political vigilantism on the security landscape in Ghana. The specific objectives are:

1. To identify the key factors that contribute to the rise of political vigilante groups.
2. To investigate the reasons for the upward thrust of political vigilantism in Ghana
3. To analyse the political, and socio-economic impacts of political vigilantism in Ghanaian society.
4. To develop policy recommendations on political vigilantism that can be put into practice in the country.

1.3. Research Questions

The objectives of the research are guided by the following research questions:

1. What is the current and historical context behind political party vigilante groups in Ghana?
2. What is the impact of vigilante practices on community security and social cohesion in Ghana from a political perspective?
3. How can the menace of political vigilantism be effectively curbed in order to ensure national security?

2. Literature Review and Conceptual Framework

2.1. Meaning and the Evolution of Political Vigilantism

Political Vigilantism is a term used to describe the practice and activities of organised groups who tend to operate outside of the law in order to enforce their own version of order, usually on behalf (or at least ostensibly so) of an interest group or party. What began as ad-hoc groups is now quite structured with clear leadership and operational methods in Ghana. Political vigilantism has evolved in Ghana due to its political history, which is characterised by competitive multiparty democracy and intense political rivalries.

The evolution of political vigilantism in Ghana has been divided into three stages by Aning and Lartey (2021); (a) the pre-independence era (b) the post-independence period, and (c) the contemporary phase. In the lead-up to independence, political violence existed in a less structured and more ad hoc form; post-independence saw such violence become far more organised. These groups have been condemned, outlawed or proscribed by many sections of the Ghanaian society. The modern era has seen the organization of groups in a political party framework to be involved heavily on their respective sides during elections.

2.2. Theoretical Framework

There are two main theories on which the study of political vigilantism in Ghana stems.

Social Contract Theory: This theory states that the legitimacy of a state is derived from this contract/agreement between community and government where governing authorities provide order and security in response to citizens' loyalty to an organised political unit, such as a nation or city-state. In the context of democracy, political vigilantism can be interpreted as an erosion of such a social contract. It must be noted, that citizens or groups act outside the boundaries defined by law and order if they believe that state-borne security manacles are not being met (Murphy 2020).

State Fragility Theory: The state fragility theory analyses how deficient, or corrupted conditions within the world of states result in non-state actors attaining functions that belong exclusively to a [nation]State. In Ghana, this phenomenon may be better recognised with political vigilantism where a hollow security and judiciary facilitates the formation of these vigilante groups (Rotberg 2003).

2.3. Political Vigilantism from a Global Perspective

Political vigilantism is not new in Ghana. The same trend has been seen in nations like Nigeria, Kenya and many parts of Latin America & India. The Bakassi Boys and the Odua People's Congress in Nigeria, for example, are groups with political ends that have often stepped into the void created by an inadequate state security apparatus (Agbibo 2018). The use of militia has been found in Kenya, where hired political militias have fostered election violence to undermine democratic processes (Mwangi 2012).

Comparative studies reveal that political vigilantism tends to occur where state institutions are weak, there is high political competition and there is a lack of trust in the formal security apparatus. Together these global perspectives shed light on several factors that contribute to political vigilantism and reveal some of the frustrations associated with addressing it.

2.4. Historical Context of Political Vigilantism in Ghana

As stated earlier, political vigilantism in Ghana dates back to the pre-independence era and some political activism resulted in violence. After independence, this terrain changed somewhat with the emergence of political parties and the advent of multiparty democracy. The 1990s saw the emergence of political vigilante groups following the transition to democratic rule in Ghana.

Over the years, political vigilante groups have come to stay and they tend to make their presence felt during elections. Members of these extremist groups have carried out violence, such as brawling with counter-protesters during attempted marches on political opponents and assaults against politicians. The visibility of these groups and their activities has further intensified the level of concern and debate held by the populace, even on social media.

2.5. Recent Trends and Developments

Current developments suggest a surge in the activities of political vigilante groups especially leading up to elections. Increasingly these groups have become better organised, they mobilise over social media more—heading into hate-filled corners of society and making it the norm instead. These incidents include the 2017 Delta Force court attack in Kumasi and more recently, the 2020 electoral violence involving various vigilante groups (Gyampo, 2020).

2.6. Effects of Political Vigilantism on Security

The broader endangerment of Ghana's security and stability as a nation by political vigilantism includes:

- **Social Impacts:** Vigilante activities result in loss of lives, injuries and destruction of properties which makes the members of society always feel unsafe.
- **Economic repercussions:** Vigilante-related violence disrupts local economies. This tends to reduce the already minimal investment opportunities in the country and ultimately creates an economic standstill.
- **Political impacts:** Political vigilantism threatens our democratic processes by reducing public confidence in political institutions and the rule of law.

3. Methodology

3.1. Research Design

The study followed mixed-methods research strategies to capture the qualitative and quantitative methodologies needed for a more complete picture of this phenomenon across Ghana. This approach permitted in-depth investigation of complex social processes, and at the same time provided quantifiable evidence to support qualitative findings (Cresswell, 2014).

3.2. Data Collection Methods

- Semi-structured interviews with key stakeholders, such as political party functionaries, security personnel and vigilantes This method allows a broad exploration of the opinions and experiences of respondents.
- Descriptive and numerical data were obtained using surveys — questionnaires sent out to gain diverse perspectives from the general populace on thoughts of political vigilantism. These surveys had a mixture of closed as well as open-ended questions to cover all possible information fields.
- Literature: The study reviewed existing literature from government documents, academic journal articles and news stories that helped structure the findings or offer alternative interpretations.

3.3. Sampling Techniques

Purposive sampling strategy was used in this research to purposely choose individuals for interviews and surveys who have first-hand knowledge or experience with the phenomenon of political vigilantism in Ghana. It ensured that the information obtained was valid and informative.

3.4. Data Analysis Procedures

Thematic analysis was used to identify patterns and themes that emerged during the interviews and open-ended survey responses for analysing the qualitative data. We also carried out a descriptive statistical analysis of the quantitative data from the survey to provide a comprehensive overview of major trends and perceptions regarding political vigilantism.

3.5. Ethical Considerations

This study adhered to the ethical guidelines, obtaining participants' consent for inclusion and ensuring confidentiality of information, while also not exposing the names of respondents. Before any collection of the data, ethical approval was received from institutional review boards.

4. Findings and Discussion

4.1. The Nature and Dynamics of Political Vigilantism in Ghana

In Ghana, political vigilantism has been characterised by the activities of organised groups that aligned themselves to major and minor forms of political organisations notably between pro-New Patriotic Party (NPP) vigilante groups or supporters as well as Pro-National Democratic Congress NDC buds throughout post-1992 multiparty era until recent times. These groups, like the Delta Force and Invisible Forces (linked to NPP), as well as the Azorka Boys (NDC-related) operated with varying degrees of organisation. These activities ranged from providing security at political rallies to participating in violent adversarial confrontations.

The groups functioned operationally around procedures for recruitment, training, and deployment that closely resembled those associated with official security services. These vigilante organisations, similar to the official security agencies use terror against citizens but with the distinction that they operate supra-legal or extra-judicial as compared to state security; using their connection to political parties to insulate themselves from prosecution. These groups are especially noticeable during elections when they exert themselves to influence election results through intimidation of returning officers or ballot snatching, or promoting their candidates at gunpoint.

In truth, social media investigation and interviews with political party officials and security agents reveal that these groups came into existence largely due to feelings among their members that they need backup protection in order to augment the inadequacy of governmental law enforcement measures. They justified their role by arguing that they are a necessary evil, beneficial to protect the interests of each other's flock. This was supported by a wide lack of trust in the good faith and effectiveness of government security agencies.

4.2. Case Studies

Ghana has had a couple of high-profile incidents which depicted the power political vigilantism wields. A notable occurrence was in 2017 at a court building in Kumasi when members of the Delta Force attacked the court. They forcibly entered the courtroom for their comrades who were on trial for previous violent actions that they had committed. This incident not only broadcast the brashness and unaccountable manner these organisations conducted themselves but also revealed serious inadequacies in the state's ability to maintain law & order.

On polling day for the general elections in 2020, vigilantes captured polling units and carried out assaults that led to snatching of ballot boxes. It further disrupted the voting process and subsequently created a vacuum of doubt about the perpetuation of Ghana's democracy.

The case studies provide a lens into how political vigilante groups have compromised the state and distorted politics. They also illustrate how difficult it is for law enforcement to rein in these gangs, largely because they enjoy political protection.

4.3. Factors that Contribute to Political Vigilantism

The reasons for the growth and sustenance of political vigilantism in Ghana are multi-faceted.

1. **Political Competition:** The near-perennial political competition between the NPP and NDC created parallel vigilante organisations. During a critical hotly contested era in politics, parties try to take advantage of these groups to intimidate their opponents and even amass potential votes using threats.
2. **Socio-economic inequalities:** The high rate of unemployment and deprivation have left poor youth of the nation more available for recruitment into groups like vigilante organisations. These people were often

motivated by the financial incentives and purpose-driven capacities that come with being members of such organisations.

3. **Cultural Factors:** In some communities, vigilante groups were viewed as cultural acts of 'restoration' in pursuit of justice and order where state institutions are thought corrupt or ineffective. The cultural context might justify the actions of vigilante groups and worsen efforts to mobilize public resistance against them.
4. **Weak State Institutions:** The inefficiency and malpractice in the state's security and judicial institutions have sown seeds for the wide presence of vigilante groups. Whenever residents lose faith in the state's ability to provide security or achieve justice, they may turn elsewhere for recourse and in this case, vigilante groups become a worthy option.

4.4. Implications for National Security

Political vigilantism poses the following threats to national security in Ghana:

- **Threats to Public Safety:** The aggressiveness and violent activities of vigilante organisations have caused loss of life, injuries as well as damage to properties. Such incidents create apprehension and feelings of insecurity among the masses. This weakens stability and cohesion in the country.
- **Undermining State Authority:** The fact that vigilante groups act with extreme impunity, threatens the authority of the state. This, in turn, undermines the credibility and effectiveness of state institutions like law enforcement agencies and the judiciary since cartels have a near limitless greater ability to act beyond legal constitutions than they would otherwise be able merely by subverting one single constitutional barrier.
- **Erosion of Public Trust in State Security Apparatus:** If a vigilante group unites with any one political party and can exercise influence on security activities, it impacts in the loss of public trust in the state's security institutions. If the confidence in security provisions is eroded further, there would be an increased reliance on non-state actors for security, thus reducing the capacity of the state to maintain public order.
- **Political Instability:** Political unrest derives directly from the friction of vigilante organizations which creates hotspots and flashpoints, especially during elections as a little spark could lead to widespread disturbances. They create instability which disrupts democratic processes and ultimately keeps investors away, thus retarding the country's economic progress.

As Ghana moves towards the general elections of 2024, there is a need for renewed focus on political vigilantism. As historical antecedents have suggested, vigilante groups get a free rein as the major political parties rouse their members for electioneering purposes. The involvement of bodies such as the Delta Force and Azorka Boys that have existing affiliations to influential political parties causes fear of violence and interference during elections. The upcoming Ghana 2024 elections are supposed to serve as an acid test of the nation's democratic determination and preparedness towards eradicating political vigilantism. The effectiveness of new laws and legislative measures in taking down vigilante groups will be tested. Nonetheless, the underlying socio-economic and political factors that are responsible for their genesis—such as intense internal competition among politicians, fiscal woes and poor government institutions—are far from intractable. The success of the government, civil society and international partners' efforts leading up to the elections is essential for determining Ghana's ability to secure a violent-free passage through this phase and define how crisis-proof its democratic mechanisms can be.

4.5. Quantitative Data Analysis

Table 1 below summarises the survey responses from the general public regarding their perceptions of political vigilantism in Ghana.

Table 1: Survey Responses on Political Vigilantism

Survey Question	Response Options	Percentage (%)
Awareness of political vigilante groups in Ghana	Very aware	65%
	Somewhat aware	25%
	Not aware	10%

Survey Question	Response Options	Percentage (%)
Affected by vigilante group activities	Yes	40%
	No	60%
Perception of the impact of vigilante groups on the electoral process	Very negative	55%
	Negative	30%
	Neutral	10%
	Positive	3%
	Very positive	2%
Belief in political party support for vigilante groups	Strongly agree	50%
	Agree	30%
	Neutral	10%
	Disagree	7%
	Strongly disagree	3%
Effectiveness of government in dealing with political vigilantism	Very effective	5%
	Effective	10%
	Neutral	25%
	Ineffective	30%
	Very ineffective	30%
Feeling of safety during election periods	Yes	20%
	No	65%
	Not sure	15%

According to the survey data, a large part of the populace is already aware of political vigilantism organisations as 65% showed a very high level of awareness. More importantly, 40% of respondents said they had been personally affected by the work carried out by these organisations. On the impact of vigilante groups on politics, about 85% of the participants hold the view that they have a generally bad or very negative effect.

About 80% of the respondents agree or strongly agree that the existence of vigilante groups has been endorsed and perpetuated by their involvement with political parties. The respondents also did not believe the government's effort or capacity to positively end political vigilantism in the country, as 60% considered the efforts mostly unsuccessful. Also, about 65% of the respondents noted that they feel an unsafe atmosphere during election seasons due to vigilante outfits.

The quantitative data corroborate the qualitative account provided through interviews and documents, revealing a widespread activity of political vigilantism with potentially serious implications for national security and democratic processes in Ghana.

4.6. Policy Recommendations

From the foregoing findings the following recommendations are made:

- 1. Enhancing the Legal Framework:** There should be legal reforms to address the societal deficiencies and loopholes that give rise to political vigilantism. Strengthening the application of existing regulations, introducing new laws directly targeting vigilante activities and providing better means for persecuting those who are found guilty of acts of political vigilantism will be most beneficial.
- 2. Increasing Law Enforcement Capacity:** Improving the capabilities of law enforcement authorities to address incidents related to vigilantism is critical. This intervention might include better-funded capacity

building, enhanced resources and even deeper co-operation among security and law enforcement agencies.

3. **Political Accountability:** There should also be a mechanism for holding political parties and their leadership accountable for their role in incubating vigilantism. This can entail setting up standards for greater transparency, tightening the control over political parties and enforcing penalties against all forms of violence in politics.
4. **Citizen Engagement and Public Awareness:** Community and public education on the signs, dangers, consequences and ways to avoid political vigilantism will help the populace make more informed decisions about vigilantism. This might involve community policing initiatives, public education programmes and activities that help to build trust between the communities and the police.
5. **International Cooperation:** Finally, the Ghana government should consider collaboration with allies from the international community to address political vigilantism in the country. This may involve partnerships with international agencies, providing specific assistance (whether logistic, financial or technical support), and learning from best practices elsewhere in the world.

5. Conclusion

5.1. Summary of Key Findings

This study focused on political vigilantism in Ghana as a problem of organised group behaviour with strong partisan linkages. These organisations represent a real threat to national security by compromising state responsibilities over public order and safety while undermining the confidence of the populace in the established security institutions. Factors that fuel the perpetuation of political vigilantism include political rivalry, socioeconomic disparities and cultural traditions as well as underfunded and ill-equipped state institutions.

5.2. Relevance to the Current Literature

This paper is a significant contribution to the literature on political vigilantism and security in Ghana, as it extensively examines both the manifestations of this phenomenon and its impact. These are all valuable insights into how these vigilante groups operate, why they do what they do and their broad range of implications on national security. The findings and recommendations proposed could be useful in the formulation of policies to tackle or eliminate political vigilantism, as well as inspire actions — both tactical and strategic, to combat it.

5.3. Recommendations for Further Research

Further studies into the development of long-term interventions that would manage political vigilantism and prevent it from destabilising Ghana's nascent democratic dispensation. The comparison with other countries facing similar challenges can provide valuable insights as well. In addition, investigating the role of digital technology and social media in designing and coordinating vigilante activities can shed new light on how to address the phenomenon.

Author Contributions: All authors contributed to this research.

Funding: Not applicable.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Informed Consent Statement/Ethics Approval: Not applicable.

References

- Agbibo, D. E. (2018). Protectors or predators? The embedded problem of police corruption and political vigilantism in Nigeria. *African Affairs*, 117(469), 409-432.
- Aning, K., & Lartey, E. (2021). Political vigilantism in Ghana: A threat to democracy and national security. *African Security Review*, 30(1), 1-15.
- Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D. (2023). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches (6th ed.)*. Sage publications.
- Gyampo, R. E. (2020). Vigilantism and electoral violence in Ghana's Fourth Republic. *Journal of Contemporary African Studies*, 38(3), 400-417.
- Murphy, C. (2020). The social contract revisited: Political legitimacy and civil disobedience in democratic societies. *Political Studies Review*, 18(1), 56-71.
- Mwangi, O. G. (2012). Political vigilantism and electoral violence in Kenya. *Journal of Modern African Studies*, 50(4), 513-531.
- Rotberg, R. I. (2003). *State failure and state weakness in a time of terror*. Brookings Institution Press.